

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of copper(II) using 1,5-diphenyl-1,4-pentadien-3-oxime

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1,5-Diphenyl-1,4-pentadien-3-oxime (DPPDO) has been identified as a sensitive and selective analytical reagent for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper(II). This reagent reacts with copper(II) in the pH range of 2.0–12.0 to form a yellowish-red 1 : 1 complex in chloroform with a absorbance maximum at 503 nm having molar absorptivity and Sandell's Sensitivity values of $1.57 \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.004065 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The developed extractive spectrophotometric method has successfully been employed for the determination of Cu^{II} in leafy vegetables etc.

Determination of copper in micro amounts via the solvent extraction into *n*-butanol or cyclohexanone in the presence of the oxime was reported earlier¹. Preconcentration based on complexation of metal ions with oximes are well known. In the present investigation, 1,5-diphenyl-1,4-pentadien-3-oxime (DPPDO) is proposed as a complexing agent for the determination of copper(II).

Results and discussion

Copper(II) reacts with 1,5-diphenyl-1,4-pentadien-3-oxime to form a yellowish-red 1 : 1 complex in Britton-Robinson buffer of pH 7.5. This complex is extracted into the chloroform and the organic extract shows a maximum absorption at 503 nm. The formation of the complex and its extraction into chloroform is instantaneous. The complex is stable for more than 48 h. The conditions for effective extraction are improved by studying the effect of various factors such as pH, reagent concentration, choice of solvent in order to develop a sensitive and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper(II).

The absorption spectrum of the Cu^{II} -DPPDO complex is recorded against the reagent blank. Similarly, the absorption spectrum of the reagent is recorded against the solvent as blank. The spectra obtained reveal that the Cu^{II} -DPPDO complex and the reagent have maximum absorbances at 503 nm and 424 nm respectively. Further absorbance measurements of the complex are made at 503 nm.

The pH of the solution had a marked effect on the formation and extraction of the ion associate. The experiments were performed using the buffers of pH range 2.0–12.0. The quantitative extraction was maximum at pH 7.5 for

copper with a constant reagent concentration of 1 ml of $1.98 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Hence, considering 7.5 as optimum pH for the determination of copper(II). The extraction of Cu^{II} -DPPDO complex into various organic solvents is studied. The percentages of extraction of Cu^{II} as its complex in each of the following solvents are 1-butanol (45%), benzene (25%), carbon tetrachloride (15%), chlorobenzene (35%), cyclohexanol (40%), chloroform (98.5%), and 1-propyl acetate (38%). Among all the solvents tested, chloroform is found to extract the complex most effectively. Hence, chloroform is chosen for further investigations. The effect of reagent concentration is studied by keeping 2 ml of 10.0 μg copper(II) solution and 3 ml of pH 7.5 buffer constant. The results show that a 12.5 fold molar excess of reagent to that of metal ion is necessary for maximum colour development of the complex. Hence, a 12.5 fold molar excess of the reagent is maintained for maximum extraction of copper(II).

The present study indicate that Beer's law is obeyed for copper(II) over the concentration range 0.5–5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The molar absorptivity of the complex is calculated as $1.57 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex obtained from Beer's law, distribution ratio $D = 0.001$, $S = 0.004065 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. An excellent linearity with correlation coefficient value of 0.98 is obtained for Cu^{II} -DPPDO complex.

The composition of the Cu^{II} -DPPDO complex is established by the slope analysis method. The distribution coefficient (D) of copper(II) is calculated at different molar concentrations of DPPDO. The logarithmic plot of D versus

[DPPDO]_M straight line with a slope of 1.0, indicating that the composition of the extracted species is 1 : 1. Interference of a number of cations and anions are studied to estimate the absorbances of Cu^{II}-DPPDO complex. Cr^{VI}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II} and Se^{IV} interfere, even when present in trace amounts. In the presence of thiosulfate and cyanide, extraction of copper(II) is not possible. About 1 ml of citrate solution was employed as masking agent for Ni^{II} and Fe^{II}. Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} and Co^{II} are masked by 2 ml of 1% thiocyanate. Mn^{II} and Se^{IV} are masked by fluoride. Cr^{VI} was masked by 0.5 ml of 1% EDTA prior to the extraction copper(II). The tolerance limit of citrate and thiocyanate is 2000 ppm.

Applications :

The proposed spectrophotometric method could be more valuable for the determination of Cu^{II} in biological and as well as environmental samples.

100 mg of dried leafy sample was taken into a 100 ml long-necked glass flask to this 4 ml of 1 : 1 mixture of HNO₃ and HClO₄ was added. The sample was kept in an acid mixture overnight. A pre-cleaned glass funnel was inserted into a glassware to prevent rapid evaporation. During this digestion procedure, three separate additions of HNO₃ were added and then cooled to the room temperature and the contents were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and made upto volume with triply distilled water. The analysis of copper(II) is carried out by employing the recommended general procedure. These results are checked with parallel determinations by direct atomic absorption spectrometry. The values are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Determination of copper(II) in leafy vegetables

Sample	Copper(II) ^a found (mg/g)		S.D.	R.S.D.%
	AAS method	Present method		
Standard samples : (known samples)		0.0165		
Pappukooraku (<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>)	0.0206	0.0205	0.0014	6.87
Chukkaku (<i>Rumex vesicarius</i>)	0.0194	0.0191	0.0005	2.72
Tutikoora (<i>Ipomoea reptanas</i>)	0.0314	0.0296	0.0023	7.80
Chammaku (<i>Colacasia antiquorum</i>)	0.0298	0.0292	0.0009	3.17
Thotakoora (<i>Amaranthus gangeticus</i>)	0.0321	0.0304	0.0020	6.67

^aAverage of four determinations.

Table 2. Determination of copper(II) in medicinally important leaves

Sample	Copper(II) ^a found (µg/g)		S.D.	R.S.D.%
	AAS method	Present method		
<i>Adrographis paniculata</i>	0.4704	0.4693	0.0001	0.18
<i>Enicostemma littorale</i>	0.5412	0.5405	0.0005	0.10
<i>Hamelia patens</i>	0.2582	0.2555	0.0038	1.49
<i>Sida acuta</i>	0.9647	0.9632	0.0023	0.24
<i>Oldenlandia</i>	1.6705	1.6722	0.0041	0.28
<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i>	0.3764	0.3730	0.0030	0.82
<i>Symbopagan citratus</i>	0.1176	0.1168	0.0003	0.22
<i>Clione viscosa</i>	0.3762	0.3761	0.0004	0.12

Materials and methods :

A Shimadzu 240 UV-VIS spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm quartz cell is used for absorbance studies. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter is used for pH measurement. A Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer is used for the comparison of results. All reagents used are of analytical reagent grade, unless otherwise stated.

2.680 g of cupric chloride was dissolved in deionised triply distilled water containing 1 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1000 ml and standardized by iodometry. This stock solution is further diluted, whenever necessary, with triple distilled water.

Synthesis of 1,5-diphenyl-1,4-pentadien-3-oxime (DPPDO) : DPPDO is synthesized and recrystallised according to Dore² by taking 1 g of bischalcone into a round bottom flask, dissolved in little methanol to this nearly 1 g of (NH₂OH.HCl) hydroxylamine-hydrochloride and 1 ml of NaOH were added then refluxed on a water bath for nearly 5 h. Then cooled to the room temperature and poured on to the crushed ice and then filtered, light yellow colored solid was thus obtained. Then it was recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Ascertaining the melting point and elemental analysis checked the purity of the reagent by TLC. A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ stock solution is prepared by dissolving 2.49 g of DPPDO in an aqueous dimethylformamide.

A 2.47 g of boric acid, 2.3 ml of CH₃COOH and 2.3 ml of H₃PO₄ are dissolved in little double distilled water and made up to 1000 ml to make 0.04 M concentration. To this 0.2 M NaOH is added to get desired pH.

Tirumala hills are the treasure of a large number of medicinally important leafy samples and such samples were collected in the forest area (particularly in the regions unexposed to pollution). Leafy vegetables are taken from Tirupati market. All possible precautions are taken at various stages starting from the sample containers, collection and storage, processing and analyzing the samples.

General procedure :

Different aliquots of 10 ml of solutions each containing 3 ml of buffer (pH 7.5), 3 ml of 1.98×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ 1,5-diphenyl-1,4-pentadiene-3-oxime reagent and 1 ml of magnesium sulphate solutions, are taken into different separatory funnels. Varying amounts of Cu^{II}, 5–50 µg, are added to these solutions. Each solution is shaken with 5 ml portions of chloroform for 30 s each time. The organic phases

are mixed and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the organic phases are recorded at 503 nm and a graph is plotted between the amount of copper(II) and its absorbance.

References

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2. J. C. Dore, *et al.*, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1975, **94**, 225.